

ISSUES OF RESPONSIBILITY FOR INFORMATION DISSEMINATED BY BLOGGERS AND SOCIAL NETWORK USERS

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Abstract: The article analyzes the problem of spreading unfounded information by bloggers and social network users and its impact on society. Consequences of unwarranted information dissemination, liability issues and international experience are explored. Also, legal mechanisms related to this problem were considered within the framework of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Measures to prevent the spread of false information on social networks have been proposed.

Keywords: blogger, social network, disinformation, disinformation, accountability, legislation, fact-checking, mass media, media literacy, public safety.

Issues of responsibility for unjustified dissemination of information by bloggers and social network users.

In the current digital age, as a result of the development of information technologies and the popularization of social networks, the speed and volume of information flow in society have increased significantly. Today, every user, especially bloggers and social media activists, is becoming influencers who influence society. At the same time, the authenticity, factual basis of the information disseminated by these entities, or their impact on security and social stability are of great importance. The dissemination of unfounded information, that is, without logical, factual, and legal grounds, can often exacerbate an atmosphere of uncertainty, mistrust, and social contradictions in society.

The issue of disseminating unfounded information is a pressing problem not only for active users, but also for the media, internet platforms, and government agencies. Analyses show that the dissemination of unfounded information spreads rapidly due to internet speed and anonymity, and complex legal and technical measures are required to eliminate them[1]. In particular, the dissemination of false information by bloggers can reduce the information critical ability of citizens and lead to a disruption of the social environment in society[2].

Legally, relations related to the dissemination of unfounded information in the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated by the Law "On Informatization," the Criminal Code, the Code of Administrative Offenses, and other relevant legislative acts[3]. For example, Article 139 of the Criminal Code provides for liability for defamation, while Article 140 provides for liability for insult, and these norms also apply in the digital space[4]. In addition, administrative penalties are applied for the dissemination of unfounded, false information via the Internet[5]. However, currently, the lack of clarity in the legal status of blogger activity and insufficient formation of liability mechanisms remain a problem.

Referring to international experience, the German "NetzDG Act"[6], the French "Information Manipulation Law"[7], and the Russian Federation's "Laws against Digital Fake Information"[8], serve as examples for taking strict measures against the dissemination of

unfounded information on social networks. These laws increased the responsibility of internet platforms, as well as obligated them to promptly remove unfounded content. Foreign experience in this area can also be applied to the legal system of Uzbekistan.

In order to ensure social and information security, it is necessary to increase the legal and moral responsibility of bloggers and social network users in the dissemination of information. This can be achieved by adopting special regulatory legal acts, improving monitoring systems, and increasing the information literacy of citizens. Such measures serve to ensure the authenticity and transparency of information in society[9].

In conclusion, it can be said that the spread of unfounded information in the digital environment negatively affects social stability and threatens human rights. Therefore, it is important to clearly define the norms of responsibility for bloggers and social network users, and to establish effective cooperation between the public and government bodies. This problem can be minimized by increasing the information critical capacity of citizens and strengthening the monitoring of internet platforms.

There are a number of problems related to this topic, which I will cite.

1. Lack of a clear legal description. The lack of a clear legal definition of the concept of a blogger leads to ambiguities in the application of liability measures against these subjects. Legislation does not clearly regulate the activities, status, and obligations of a blogger.

2. Vulnerability of mechanisms for identifying unfounded information. Especially under conditions of a rapidly spreading information flow, the mechanisms for verifying false or fake information through fact-checking are poorly developed. This leads to the widespread dissemination of non-source-based information.

3. Technical problems in the implementation of responsibility. Anonymity on the Internet and the difficulty in identifying users make it difficult to hold them accountable.

4. Low level of information literacy. Among citizens, especially young people, the low ability to think critically and analyze information makes them prone to trusting information with an uncertain source.

5. Responsibility of platforms. The policies of social networks, which assume that they are not responsible for the information disseminated, hinder the effective fight against unfounded information.

In order to eliminate the above problems, I propose the following proposals:

1. Legal regulation of blogger activity. A separate law "On Blogging Activities" should be adopted. It should clearly define the rights and obligations of bloggers, restrictions on the dissemination of information, and liability measures.

2. Implementation of information verification systems. It is possible to combat the spread of false information by creating national or state-supported fact-checking platforms.

3. Increasing information literacy. It is necessary to organize regular training courses and trainings to improve media literacy among the population, especially school and university students.

4. Increasing the responsibility of platforms. Social network operators should be legally obligated to identify and suppress unfounded information.

5. International cooperation. In the fight against false information disseminated on the Internet, it is important to study foreign experience and technologies and integrate them into national practice.

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